

Standard Operating Procedure

Title: Sample Preparation Protocol for the Extraction and Raman analysis of Small Microplastics in Infant Milk Formula

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Document change history and approval

1. Scope and application

This standard operating procedure (SOP) describes the preparation of commercial infant milk formula samples for the extraction of microplastics (MPs, 1-1000 μm , ISO/TR 21960:2020) [1]. Due to the high complexity of the matrix, which contains both macro- and micronutrients (e.g., proteins, carbohydrates, and fats), the SOP is specifically designed to efficiently remove organic matter while preserving the physical integrity of MPs. The resulting samples are suitable for vibrational spectroscopy analyses – particularly μ -Raman spectroscopy – for the chemical identification, enumeration, and size distribution of microplastics particles. The SOP is aligned with the analytical approach whose accuracy was assessed in *Putzu et al., Talanta Open (2025)*[2].

2. Terms, definitions and normative references

(1) “**plastic**

material which contains as an essential ingredient a high polymer (3.1) and which, at some stage in its processing into finished products, can be shaped by flow.

Note 1 to entry: Plastics consists mainly of polymers and minor contents of additives (3.7).

Note 2 to entry: Supplementary to the term “plastic”, “plastic product” is also used. According to ISO 472, a plastic product represents “any material or combination of materials, semi-finished or finished product that is within the scope of ISO/TC 61, Plastics”.

Note 3 to entry: Plastics comprise both thermoplastic (3.3) and thermoset (3.4) materials.” [1]

(2) “**microplastic**

any solid plastic particle insoluble in water with any dimension between 1 μm and 1000 μm (=1 mm).

Note 1 to entry: This term relates to plastic materials within the scope of ISO/TC 61. Rubber, fibers, cosmetic means, etc. are not within the scope.

Note 2 to entry: Typically, a microplastic object represents a particle intentionally added to end-user products, such as cosmetic means, coatings, paints, etc. A microplastic object can also result as a fragment of the respective article.

Note 3 to entry: Microplastics may show various shapes.

Note 4 to entry: The defined dimension is related to the longest distance of the particle". [1]

(3) "polymer

chemical compounds or mixture of compounds consisting of repeating structural units created through polymerization.

Note 1 to entry: In practice above 10 000 Dalton.

Note 2 to entry: Polymers comprise both plastics and elastomers. The latter is excluded from the scope of ISO/TC 61." [1]

(4) "Raman spectroscopy

Spectroscopy in which the Raman effect is used to investigate molecular energy levels" according to ISO 16094-2:2025 [3]

(5) "Raman effect

Scattered light, associated with molecules illuminated with monochromatic light, characterized by an energy loss or gain arising from rotational or vibrational excitations" according to ISO 16094-2:2025 [3]

3. Abbreviated terms

[SOP] Standard operating procedure

[MPs] Microplastics

[PET] Polyethylene terephthalate

[PS] Polystyrene

[RL] Reporting limit

4. Method principle

The sample preparation protocol for MPs extraction from infant milk formula is based on a two-step digestion process combining multi-enzymatic digestion with hot alkaline hydrolysis. Enzymes are first employed to degrade the protein fraction, reducing the matrix complexity. A chelating agent is added to enhance enzymatic effect and remove metal ion such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{2+} . In the final step, hot alkaline hydrolysis degrades the lipid fraction, reducing viscosity and completing the removal of organic matter. This sequence preserves intact MP particles, including more sensitive polymer such as PET, which may degrade under harsh oxidative or highly alkaline conditions (e.g., temperatures above its glass transition) [4,5]. The procedure ensures reliable recovery across different particle size fractions, including the smallest particles, enabling accurate subsequent analysis.

5. Safety procedures and precautions

Standard laboratory safety procedures, including those specific to the local laboratory, must be always followed. Special care is required when handling chemical reagents and microplastics. Particles smaller than 40 μm can become airborne, and those smaller than 10 μm can be inhaled, posing an inhalation hazard. Work under a fume hood, use personal protective equipment (e.g. lab coat, gloves), and avoid plastic-based consumables to prevent contamination.

6.1 Apparatus and equipment

This section is to list and specify all equipment used in the procedure:

- 250 mL glass bottles and flasks
- 10-20 mL glass flasks
- Aluminum foil
- Stainless steel spoon

- Ultrasonic Cleaner (DU-45, 180W)
- Magnetic stirrer with heating plate
- Filtration unit (100 mL funnel, glass holder with 13 mm frit)
- Vacuum pump
- Macroporus Silicon membrane (5 μm porosity, 9 x 9 mm diameter, 490 μm pore length, 12 μm pitch; SmartMembrane)
- Custom-made filter holder
- Tweezers
- Glass pipettes
- Drying oven
- Glass petri dishes
- Filter holder for analysis
- Micro syringe Filter Holder 25mm, Luer-lok, stainless steel
- PVDF membrane filter (0.65 μm , 25 mm)
- Silver membrane filter (5 μm , 25 mm)

6.2 Chemicals, reference materials and reagents

- Organic 1 First Infant Baby Milk Powder
- Ultrapure water (Milli-Q[®] IQ 7000, Merck Millipore, Germany)
- Multi-enzymatic detergent (Prozyme Active Deconex, Borer Chemie AG)
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid sodium salt (EDTA-Na 0.5 M, pH 8, Invitrogen, ThermoFisher Scientific)
- Tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH 25 % v/v, Sigma-Aldrich)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH 2.5 M, PanReac AppliChem ITW Reagents)
- Nitric acid (HNO₃ 5 % v/v in water, Carlo Erba Reagents GmbH)
- Ethanol absolute anhydrous 99.9 % (Carlo Erba Reagents GmbH)
- Triton™ X-100 (0.01 % v/v in water, Thermo Fisher Scientific)
- Acetone 99.9 % (Carlo Erba Reagents GmbH)

6.3 Sample

This section lists the nature of the samples and the amount of sample that is being processed.

This SOP applies exclusively to milk powder samples. A 14 % w/v suspension of powdered milk is prepared using ultrapure water and mixed at 40 °C for 15 min in a shaking water bath (Ultrasonic Cleaner DU-45, 180 W). A 25 mL aliquot of the reconstituted milk is then mixed with 20 mL of ultrapure water, constituting the sample volume to be processed for digestion and subsequent analysis.

6.4 Equipment preparation

Work as clean as possible, especially plastic-free, to avoid contamination.

All equipment (e.g., bottles, Petri dishes, beakers, filters, tweezers, filtering units) are thoroughly cleaned with Triton™ X-100 (0.01 % v/v in ultrapure water), acetone (99.9 %), and 90% v/v solution of ethanol (99.9 %) in ultrapure water, then covered with aluminum foil.

Reagents were prepared under the same controlled conditions in clean beakers, using glass pipettes for transfers, and protected with aluminum foil before and after use to minimize contamination. Samples remained covered with foil throughout all preparation steps, including filtration, except for brief periods when pouring. Additional precautions including washing hands, avoiding make up, wearing a cotton lab, and performing all sample handling under a fume hood are followed to minimize contamination.

6.5 Sample preparation protocol

- Weigh 14 g of powdered milk and dilute in 100 mL of ultrapure water (14 % w/v).
- Transfer to a glass bottle, cover with foil, and sonicate at 40 °C for 15 min.
- Withdraw 25 mL of reconstituted milk and mix with 20 mL of ultrapure water containing spiked MP particles (e.g., PS standards or dissolved PET reference material tablet) in a glass beaker.
- Place on a magnetic stirrer at 40 °C.

- Sequentially add:
 - 2 mL of multi-enzymatic detergent (stir 2 min);
 - 10 mL of EDTA-Na (0.5 M, pH 8) (stir 3 min);
 - 2 mL of TMAH (25 % v/v).

- Increase temperature to 80 °C.
- Perform hot filtration immediately to prevent membrane clogging.
- Rinse sequentially with:
 - 5 mL ultrapure water;
 - 5 mL 5% v/v HNO₃;
 - 10 mL ultrapure water.

- Transfer the filtered sample to a clean holder, dry at 50 °C for ≥ 30 min, and store in covered Petri dishes.
- Proceed with vibrational spectroscopy analysis.

7. Calculation of results

The efficiency of the protocol is verified by spiking the reconstituted milk with certified spherical PS standards (Thermo Scientific™ COUNT-CAL™ Particle Size Standards: 70 µm; 3000 ± 300 (SD), RSD 10% particles per mL), characterized by a known shape, particle number, and size and further using PET reference material (RM) tablet (5-100 µm), produced within the PlasticTrace project [6]. The recovery of MP particles after the extraction procedure has been calculated for both materials as follows:

$$\text{Recovery (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of particles recovered after the procedure}}{\text{Number of particles originally introduced}} \times 100$$

(Equation 1)

7.1 Visual sorting

The determination of PS particles is conducted by visual sorting under optical microscopy, counting the particles retained on the Si filter subsequent to filtration. Three replicates were performed, and recovery was calculated using Equation 1 based on the mean values obtained from the independent replicates. Raman spectra were acquired on selected particles to confirm the polymer identity. The corresponding results are reported in Table 1, Sect. 9 (Reporting results).

7.1 Micro-Raman spectroscopy

PET RM (5-100 μm), produced as water-soluble tablets and tested for homogeneity and stability in terms of both mass fraction and particle number in accordance to ISO 17034:2016 [7], ISO 33405:2024 [8] and ISO 16094-2:2025 [3], were individually dissolved in ultrapure water and analyzed using μ -Raman spectroscopy to determine particle number and size distribution. Raman has been selected for its high spatial resolution and suitability for detecting small MPs. Measurements are performed with a 50 \times objective on three independent areas per filter — covering approximately 50% of the filtration area - and the mean particle count is extrapolated to the entire filter area (100 % of the filtration area). Further methodological details are provided in Putzu et al., *Talanta Open* (2025) [2] and the corresponding results are reported in Table 2 and 3, Sect. 9 (Reporting results).

8. Quality control

It is essential to perform procedural blanks using ultrapure water and apply the same sample preparation protocol to evaluate any potential background MP contamination. Each laboratory should also determine its RL — the minimum number of MPs that can be reliably quantified, depending on polymer type, size class, and standard operating conditions [9] — to ensure comparability and reliability of results [2], in accordance with ISO 16094-2:2025 [3]. The RL must be calculated for each polymer based on the results of ten procedural blanks independently

performed procedural blanks and considering the detection threshold imposed by the filter pore size, as follows:

$$RL [\text{filter pore} - \mu\text{m}] = \text{mean} (10 \text{ blanks}) + 3 \times \text{SD} (10 \text{ blanks})$$

(Equation 2)

9. Reporting of results

The number of PS and PET particles introduced and recovered after the sample preparation procedure is reported in Table 1, Table 2 and 3, respectively. MP particle counts were determined using the recovery formula (Equation 1). The high recovery obtained for both PS ($100 \pm 22\%$) and PET RM ($82 \pm 16\%$) confirms that the procedure effectively removes organic matter without loss or degradation of MPs, thereby ensuring suitability for subsequent vibrational spectroscopy analysis.

9.1 Visual sorting

Table 1. Recovery (%) of PS standard by visual sorting under optical microscopy following the sample preparation protocol, expressed as mean \pm standard deviation

MP particles	Number of MP particles originally introduced	Number of MP particles recovered after the protocol	Recovery (%)
PS	300 \pm 30 (RSD, 10%)	301 \pm 60 (RSD, 20%)	100 \pm 22

9.1 Micro-Raman spectroscopy

Table 2. Mean PET RM particle numbers per tablet (\pm SD, %RSD, n = 10) determined by μ -Raman. The table is adapted from Putzu et al.,[2]

Spectroscopic method	5-10 μm	10-20 μm	20-50 μm	50-100 μm	100-500 μm	Particle number per tablet
μ -Raman	111 \pm 49	330 \pm 62	889 \pm 58	361 \pm 29	68 \pm 14	1759 \pm 141 (8% RSD)

Table 3. Recovery (%) of PET RM by μ -Raman spectroscopy following the sample preparation protocol, expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The table is adapted from Putzu et al.,[2]

	PET particles per tablet	PET particles per tablet in Milk – after sample protocol	Recovery %
PET RM	1759 \pm 141 (RSD, 8%)	1448 \pm 253 (RSD, 17%)	82 \pm 16

10. Validation status

ILC (Interlaboratory comparison)

in house

Results can be seen [2].

11. Literature references

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